

HISTORICAL DATABASE OF SURINAME & THE CARIBBEAN

Handwritten Archival Data Structuring with Regex Recognition (HANDS-RX)

PROJECT REPORT

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1 Introduction

This project is executed by HookedOnData for the Historical Database Suriname and the Caribbean (HDSC). Its aim is to extract entities from ~24,000 Curaçao death certificates, a subset from the 1831-1950 death register data. We set up the HTR+RegEx pipeline as described in Hoek's MSc thesis [1]. This report describes the implementation and improvements made during the HANDS-RX project (9/2023-6/2024), a continuation of the HTR+RegEx project, upgraded to the HTR+GPT pipeline. We use Transkribus [2][3] for Layout Detection and HTR, and GPT-4 for Entity Extraction [4]. Each of the sections in this report describes one of our contributions, which can be summarised as follows:

- 2 The collection of 70,000+ Curaçao death certificates between 1831-1950 is filtered and a new version is released.
- 3 The HANDS-RX pipeline is executed on ~24,000 certificates that have missing entities in the Curaçao 1831-1950 death register database.
- 4 A new module is created that detects incorrect layouts from the P2PaLA model.
- 5 A new function rearranges the baselines such that two baselines of similar height are now in order of left to right.
- 6 We compared the HTR+RegEx output of 1,534 certificates from 1879-1881 against the results of a citizen science pilot.
- 7 We tested GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 as Entity Extraction method and eventually replaced the RegEx component with GPT-4.
- 8 We show that HTR+GPT is significantly better than HTR+RegEx comparing it to the 1,534 certificates transcribed in the citizen science pilot.
- 9 We give an overview of the customisation possibilities for the HANDS-RX pipeline.
- 10 We prepared 500 certificates of the Paramaribo 1929-1960 death certificate dataset and put them in sets of 50 on Transkribus to transcribe by volunteers.
- 11 We applied DBscan image clustering on the Paramaribo 1929-1960 death certificate dataset to analyse and filter this data.

2 New version Curaçao scans database

We released a new version of the Curaçao scans database 1831-1950. In this newer version, duplicates (e.g., "Griffies") are moved away from the main structure and miscellaneous certificates are moved into a dedicated folder. Our filtering technique is based on the filenames and some knowledge we have on the folder structure. The main structure of the filenames is "O.R. <year> <district> <number>", but miscellaneous scans can have a character 'a', etc. added to it. This is often an additional paper note belonging to the certificate in front. For this reason, we filtered out the scans with a character, and its corresponding certificate. Then, we looked at each last certificate from each folder, as these can be closure pages instead of death certificates. We obtain a set of 1,038 miscellaneous scans. These consist for 1/3th of some other type than a death certificate, for 1/3th of additional papers in front of death certificates and the last 1/3th are those corresponding death certificates.

We are aware not all miscellaneous certificates are removed from the main structure, meaning there will still be some noise in the pipeline. However, the majority is clean and ready for Entity Extraction in Transkribus and Python. A more complex method would be to use Machine Learning and cluster the images based on appearance. We opted for a simpler approach as lots of information was already in the file name and folder structure. Section 11 does describe image clustering on another set of death certificates, those of Paramaribo 1929-1960.

Some other notes about the Curaçao scans database:

- 1) 1869 is split into three-column format (January-May) and two-column format (June-December).
- 2) for 1870, there are no scans for the districts.

- 3) the year 1887 contains scans with lots of tearing, we advise to transcribe these manually and not process them in the HANDS-RX pipeline. The same holds for the miscellaneous scans, as they deviate from the standard layout.

The database is currently available on HookedOnData's Google Drive. Upon completion of the project, this data and the output of the HANDS-RX pipeline, will be handed over to the HDSC. All code written for this project is in our GitHub repository.¹

Figure 1. HANDS-RX model for extracting entities from Curaçao death certificates.

¹Lisa Hoek, HANDS-RX. <https://github.com/LisaHoek/HANDS-RX>.

3 HANDS-RX pipeline

Figure 1 shows the full HANDS-RX pipeline, an extension of the HTR+RegEx model. Our input data are roughly 24,000 certificates which are missing or incomplete in the current existing death register database. These are years 1879-1895, 1905-1909, 1930-1939, and 1945-1949. Our layout models are nearly perfect, unfortunately, the HTR component carries mistakes downstream to other components. As Entity Extraction method, we opt for GPT-4. The next subsections discuss for each component how this is executed. Figure 2 shows what the certificates before 1938 and after look like.

3.1 Upload documents to Transkribus

Transkribus can only handle folders of a maximum size of 3,000, so we created 9 subgroups (Table 1). These are uploaded to Transkribus using WinSCP² and the ‘upload via private FTP’ import-button in Transkribus. WinSCP is a file manager system supporting File Transfer Protocol (FTP). A benefit of using this file manager is that Transkribus can be used while uploading the scans. When uploading small sets of data, this can easily be done in the Transkribus interface using the ‘import’ button, so WinSCP is not necessary, but one would have to wait for it to finish.

Format	Years	Size	Nr of suspicious layouts (decreases after each run)
twoEarly	1879-1884	2989	322→158→136→119
	1885-1889	2759	758→207→173→155→133
	1890-1894	2502	96→52→27
	1895+1905-1907	2721	256→64→31
	1908-1909+1930	2139	51→34
	1931-1934	2967	648→556→554→494→90→88→80
	1935-1937	2373	295→36
twoLate	1938-1939 1945-1946 Stad	3095	
	1946 Buiten 1947-1949	2339	

Table 1: 1) Grouping in Transkribus, 2) Number of pages with suspicious layout that decreases when P2PaLA is applied again. Section 4 describes how the number of incorrect layouts is lowered iteratively.

Figure 2. Scan from 1879 (twoEarly format) on the left, and scan from 1949 (twoLate format) on the right.

²WinSCP. <https://winscp.net/eng/index.php?>

3.2 Layout Analysis (segmentation)

The first step of Layout Analysis is P2PaLA to create the regions. We use model ‘P2PaLA-two_Curacao’ for this on the twoEarly-format, and use ‘P2PaLA-twoLate_Curacao’ on the twoLate-format (Table 1). The first model is trained on 200 certificates using an additional 30 as validation. The second model is trained on 100+20 certificates, because the first model did not work sufficiently on data after 1938. We suspect this is because there is no clear rectangle around the certificate, and the certificates are less centred in the middle of the image (Figure 2).

Then, we apply our ‘region-correction’ method on the twoEarly-format. We refer to Section 4 for this. After multiple iterations, and manually improving the last batch, we obtain nearly perfect regions of the main certificate text (marginalia text excluded).

The last step of Layout Analysis is the creation of baselines with model ‘LA_Curacao’. We disable ‘Find Text-regions’ (regions are already made with our P2PaLA models) and enable ‘Split lines on regions’ (so baselines are created inside each region). Also, we set ‘max-dist for merging baselines’ to 0.99 as done in [1] (so it tries to merge baselines next to each other as much as possible inside regions).

3.3 HTR model

We apply the model ‘Curacao.Dutchess’ to create HTR output. This model is trained on 313 ground truth transcriptions that were created the past months and uses Transkribus’ base model The Dutchess I. It is an improvement on the model ‘HTR_Curacao.bestModel’ which was used in [1]. This model was trained on only 114 transcriptions with a smaller base model. We also trained a model using 512 ground truth transcriptions (all data available near the end of the project). Unfortunately, this model learned less well and achieved a worse CER during training. This is also visible when applying the model on a small test set (size=10). We refer to Table 2 for this. We argue this can be due to randomness during HTR training (more new trainings might give better scores), or due to how our validation set is constructed (more difficult examples). Many of our HTR trainings failed, so our CER scores increased after a certain number of epochs. We were not able to tune this properly in Transkribus’ interface. That is why we stick to ‘Curacao.Dutchess’ as our best HTR model.

HTR model	Size		Base model	CER (%)		
	Train	Val		Train	Val	Test
Curacao.Dutchess_notImproved	477	57	The Dutchess I	5.3	5.6	7.0
Curacao.Dutchess	278	35	The Dutchess I	3.0	3.71	3.9
HTR_Curacao.bestModel	99	15	Ijsberg	3.0	6.0	6.9
Default Transkribus	0	0	The Dutchess I	-	-	60

Table 2: HTR results after training and on a small test set (size=10). Layout is manually corrected before training and testing.

3.4 Pre-process texts

Once HTR is created for each baseline, we are done processing in Transkribus and export the documents to XML format. We extended the function ‘read_files’ by [5] so that the ordering of baselines is improved. More on this in Section 5. Then, we apply our cleaning function that creates one continuous string from the certificate text. This function removes newlines in such a way that hyphenations are dealt with correctly.

3.5 Apply RegEx-patterns / Make GPT-4 API calls

In the HTR+RegEx model, entities were retrieved by matching custom regular expressions on the certificates. These were created based on 100 certificates and tested on other 100 certificates and showed fairly

good results [1]. However, once applied on our first pilot dataset consisting of 1,534 certificates from 1879-1881, results were much less. A detailed evaluation described in Section 6 revealed some entity types were often not detected (failing RegExes), and HTR errors caused false RegEx matches. Table 3 shows the performances.

We observed more HTR errors for names and professions (Table 4 & 5) than in other entities, e.g., dates. Also, RegExes for the parents and partner were too difficult to create easily. That is why a transcription project was set up to first transcribe the names and professions in the certificates. This ensures transcription quality for names (which are important as they are used to link persons over various collections).

Then, in a pilot review project, the volunteers checked the manual transcriptions for the names and professions, along with the HTR+RegEx output from the remaining entities. From feedback discussions with the volunteers, we learnt that some found it annoying to see empty entries (i.e., no output from the HTR+RegEx model). It is true that in hindsight this occurred too often to call it a 'review' project³. This problem does no longer occur as we opted for GPT-4 instead of regular expressions.

Section 7 describes the results of our experiments with GPT-4. We created a Python script and customised a prompt to instruct GPT-4. A new⁴ feature from OpenAI called 'batches' enabled us to retrieve the entities in bulk (with 50% discount) by uploading a JSONL file with all the API requests to OpenAI [6]. Processing all 24,000 certificates cost us in total \$355. Section 8 shows that we obtained much better results for GPT-4 than RegExes as Entity Extraction method.

3.6 Post-process texts

A Python script now processes the output files from GPT and transforms the data into an Excel table. We add the column for the certificate number based on the file names of the scans, because those are better quality than the HTR+GPT output.

Then, we provide two extra columns with an improved output for certificate date and date of death by taking the year mentioned in the file name and substituting this in the date of the entity. For date of death, we alter the year to the year before the certificate date, if the month is later than the certificate month (e.g., a certificate from 03-01-1890 with date of death 27-12-1889). Our function altered 555 certificate dates and 719 date of deaths. Looking at 20 random certificates for certificate date, all 20 were correct revisions. Looking at 40 random certificates for date of death, 31 were correct revisions. The 9 wrong adjustments were 1) two verdicts adjusting a certificate many years ago, 2) a death two years earlier, 3) a certificate beginning of January in which the official presumably forgot the new year had already started, and 4) 5 certificates where HTR+GPT output was wrong (incorrect month) so our post-processing incorrectly adjusted the year to the year before. We argue this post-processing step results in more improvements than harm, so we included this step. Though, it does lead to some incorrect adjustments. A mistake that is often corrected is when HTR did not detect part of the year, e.g., 1930 (Een duizend negen honderd 'en dertig') should have been 1939 (Een duizend negen honderd 'negen en dertig').

The last post-processing step trying to improve HTR errors in professions is not included in our final pipeline, because our first experiments were not promising. We evaluated the HTR output of the first informant's profession (985 output values) against two lists of professions (size 542 and 1579). Changing each profession to the most similar in the list, resulted in 82 correct adjustments, but 88 wrong adjustments, e.g., incorrect HTR such as 'akslager' is corrected to 'slager' instead of 'blikslager'. We conclude our lists are not extensive enough to apply on our professions, or, the number of HTR mistakes inside a profession is too much resulting in matching a different profession. For future work, we suggest matching against a more extensive list of professions, and use the HTR+GPT output instead of HTR+RegEx.

³In traditional crowdsourcing within the HDSC, all entities are filled in by two volunteers in a standard project, then checked by a third in a review project. The HTR output showed too many mistakes and empty values to immediately use its output in the review project.

⁴Launched 15th of April 2024.

4 P2PaLA region correction

We created a Python script that draws the regions of multiple certificates on a blank canvas on top of each other, so one can quickly inspect if there are any weird shapes. One can set the number of certificates to display, run the script, then hover over a shape to see the certificate's page number. We determined a baseline rectangle that should fall within each certificate region (See Figure 3). If a region is crossing, touching or fully inside the baseline rectangle, there is a big chance the P2PaLA model failed here. So, we created a jupyter notebook that extracts these page numbers automatically.

This list of page numbers is then used in Transkribus to run P2PaLA again over these certificates. In Table 1, one can see the number of suspicious certificates drop once P2PaLA is applied several times. This is due to the weird bug in P2PaLA that it sometimes creates a chaotic, wrong layout, but when applied again, this problem can disappear. The remainder of the wrong certificates is improved manually.

For the last two groups in Table 1, the certificates look a bit different. These scans do not have a big rectangle around the certificate, which leads to a larger variety of positions of the certificate-region. We did not use our region correction technique on these two groups.

Also, the marginalia have too much variety to evaluate on one baseline. Therefore, we cannot claim anything about the quality of this section. It is possible that words or sentences are cut off if they fall outside the created marginalia-region. We did not put further effort into finding a proper evaluation for this, as the majority of the marginalia contain signatures and approvals of strikethrough.

Figure 3. The borders of 500 certificates from 1879-1884 along with the red baseline rectangle. There are some suspicious layouts with part of a region inside the red baseline.

5 Baseline order correction

After applying our custom models for regions and baselines, many of the problems described in [1] were resolved, however, one problem still occurred: wrong baseline ordering.

We added a new function to the XML script of [5], so that it also returns a list of the text lines in improved order. The algorithm used for this is as follows: if the average height difference between two text lines is less than 20 pixels, and the first baseline starts more to the right than the ending of the second baseline, swap the two lines. This is checked twice. If it still holds after three iterations, the filename is printed, because this indicates there might be something else wrong with the certificate, e.g., weird regions were created in the P2PaLA step. Note that 20 pixels is a good threshold for our Curaçaoan death certificates, this can differ in other type of data.

We tested the algorithm on the 1879-1884 data. The number of swaps that took place for these 2,989 certificates was 1,313. Many of them were at the end of the certificate, which does not consist of important entities in this project. However, once applying the RegEx-patterns on the certificates, this resulted in 250 extra matches which were empty values before. So, our baseline order correction improves the ability to localise the entities using RegExes. We did not test if this also helped GPT localise the entities.

6 Evaluation HTR+RegEx against ‘Het Volk’

To get a better idea of the performance of the HTR+RegEx model, and to evaluate how this should cooperate with crowdsourcing, we set up a pilot in HDSC’s crowdsourcing platform ‘Het Volk’ [7]. This consists of 1,534 certificates from 1879-1881. First, names and professions of all persons mentioned in the certificates were transcribed twice, because these entities performed too low in the HTR+RegEx model. Then, a review project is created in which volunteers check the two other volunteers’ output (on names and professions), plus the output from the computer model (on the other entities), and they make a final decision for each.

We assume the volunteers data to be ground truth, but important to note is that they make errors too. We have spotted some, so these results only give an indication of the performance of the HTR+RegEx model. Performance can be a bit higher than described if some volunteers wrongfully adjusted the correct model output. The HTR+RegEx performance can be a bit lower than described if volunteers forgot to correct the model. We expect both to happen (as we have seen cases of both), but do not know how often this happens. We expect the latter to occur more.

Comparing the final decisions from the volunteers against the original HTR+RegEx model output tells us something about the HTR+RegEx performance. Table 3 shows the performance. We observe many failing RegExes: around 5-15% for certificate date, age, profession, place of birth and sex, and about 30-36% for the age and profession of both informants, date of death, time of death, and date of birth. These are percentages for where the volunteers found an entity but HTR+RegEx did not.

In the end, we conclude that the HTR+RegEx performance for all entities is too low to immediately check these in the review project. When only checked by one volunteer, we are afraid not enough computer mistakes are corrected. The HTR+RegEx model is unable to locate a lot of the entities (empty fields for the volunteers), often due to mistakes in the HTR in the words surrounding the entities. There were lots of model corrections needed too. So, RegExes do not reach our desired quality.

7 Entity Extraction using GPT

In our evaluation comparing the HTR+RegEx output against HetVolk, it becomes visible how many entities are missed due to the static phrase-matching in the RegExes. Research already showed fuzzy matching is

not an improvement on this [1], but using GPT models for entity extraction might. A reason for this is that GPT might be more flexible to spelling errors, opposed to static RegExes.

7.1 Prompt to fill in the null-values

To check if GPT can help us fill in the missing values, we test GPT on 1) 'age' and 'profession' of both informants, 2) 'date_of_birth' and 3) 'date_of_death'. For each, we select 50 random certificates for which the RegExes were unable to locate the entity. Then, we define three separate prompts for the GPT model. We test both GPT-3.5 and GPT-4. (GPT-4 is often better than GPT-3.5, but it costs 20 times more.) We summarise our results as follows:

- In all cases, GPT was able to create output.
- For date_of_birth, GPT-3.5 made 14 mistakes. GPT-4 did not make any mistakes. This can happen if the model is confused what to do, e.g., it returns 'Curaçao' as date_of_birth.
- For each entity, 1 out of 5 is still incorrect, because of wrong HTR, e.g., when the HTR output is 'zes', GPT returns 'zes', but the correct transcription should have been 'zestig'. This is not GPT's fault.
- In general, 4 out of 5 values are correct. These are extra correct compared to the RegExes. We assume that GPT also works for the cases the RegExes work.

So, there seems to be a lot of potential in using GPT to remove lots of empty fields for the volunteers. Unfortunately, empty fields occur in over 90% of the certificates. So, in order to fill in those empty fields, we need to feed almost all certificates to GPT. Because of this, we might as well retrieve all entities with GPT and discard the RegExes.

7.2 Prompt to extract all entities

In this experiment, we extract all entities using GPT-3.5 and GPT-4. We selected 50 random certificates from 1879-1881. The prompt asks to distinguish between stillborn and normal certificates, to parse the times, dates and ages, and to split each name in first name(s), prefix and last name. Once applying the prompt on other years, we must first check if the certificate texts are similar such that the prompt is aligned with the certificate texts, e.g., in 1938, the certificates switch to only one informant.

We observe a couple of things. First of all, GPT-3.5 makes more mistakes than GPT-4, we spotted a certificate wrongly indicated as stillborn, two wrong certificate dates and 'bekende van' as profession. There can be even more mistakes. In a quick glance, we did not spot any of these mistakes for GPT-4. Secondly, we observed that GPT-3.5 often classifies the mother as father. Thirdly, GPT-3.5 has trouble returning a split of each name. GPT-4 does split each name, but many are incorrect, e.g., the middle name as prefix. Unfortunately, tweaking the prompt did not improve on this. As future work, we suggest fine-tuning GPT-3.5 with lots of examples how names can be split. In the final execution of the pipeline, we opted for GPT-4 to extract the entities, and name entities were not split anymore but extracted as a whole.

8 Evaluation HTR+GPT against HTR+RegEx and 'Het Volk'

This section describes the performance of the HTR+GPT model over the HTR+RegEx model, summarised in three tables.

Table 3 shows that GPT is able to retrieve more answers similar to human transcriptions. Looking at the wrong answers in more depth, they are mostly mistakes in the HTR causing incorrect extractions by GPT. The scores are also not perfect, because we are comparing against human transcriptions. Though given an extensive annotation guideline, there can be room for interpretations (e.g., how names should be split) and not all details from the annotation guideline are always followed (e.g., writing dates both as 01-01-1880 and

Entity (%Nulls)	RegEx	GPT
Certificate number	99%	-
Certificate date	83%	+12%
Age informant 1	64%	+29%
Profession informant 1	53%	+27%
Age informant 2	63%	+30%
Profession informant 2	47%	+25%
Age	81%	+1%
Profession (41%)	72%	-2%
Date of death	45%	+43%
Time of death	66%	+24%
Date of birth (19%)	61%	+14%
Place of birth	88%	+3%
Sex	93%	+5%
Marital status (54%)	89%	+0%
Mother is deceased (15%)	-	86%
Father is deceased (77%)	-	91%
Partner is deceased (88%)	-	93%

Table 3: Percentage of identical values between the human transcriptions and the HTR+RegEx model in the pilot of 1534 certificates, and the improvement of the HTR+GPT model. Between brackets is the percentage of Null values for the human transcriptions, if this is over 3%.

1-1-1880). We do account for things like this, so the scores in this report try to better resemble the actual performance. For example, we adjust both human and GPT output with lowercasing, removing trailing spaces, changing 'jaar' to 'jaren' or '00-00-1880' to '1880', and more.

Note that sometimes an entity is not mentioned in the certificate. For most entities, this occurred in <3% of the certificates, but for some, this occurred more (behind entities in Table 3). If both human transcription and computer model are either Null or '#', this adds to the percentage of similar answers.

For the deceased status of the parents and the partner, we do not give the accuracy for the HTR+RegEx model, because the latest RegExes were incomplete for the parents and non-existent for the partner. Also, their names and professions were too difficult to make RegExes for. We also left out the names of the informants and the name of the deceased, because those were not needed (already separately transcribed by the volunteers). We did add them in the HTR+GPT model, because we wanted to study its performance (Table 4 & 5). We did not add the certificate number to the GPT-4 prompt, because we could extract this from the file names with better performances than using HTR.

The profession of the deceased person was mistakenly forgotten in the transcription pilot, so this is transcribed by two student assistants. The GPT score is lower, because GPT-4 mixed up many 'zonder beroep' and 'onbekend' with '#'. (We asked GPT to answer '#' when the entity is not mentioned, and 'zonder beroep' or 'beroep onbekend' when it is marked in the certificate as having no profession.) Better GPT prompting might have solved this, but this mistake was detected after our full run over the data.

When comparing HTR+RegEx against HTR+GPT for professions in more depth, we notice that HTR+GPT returned more correct answers (607 instead of 484) and more incorrect answers (468 instead of 425), due to it always giving some answer opposed to RegExes that regularly failed. It could be argued that HTR+GPT performed better than HTR+RegEx, especially if we do not treat mix-ups of 'zonder beroep' and '#' as incorrect answers.

The 1% for certificate number demonstrates the transcribers do not generate perfect results, because these

adjustments were actually incorrect. In addition, there are biases in this experiment, because the volunteers saw the HTR+RegEx output while transcribing. However, each percentage still gives us an idea of the performance of the HTR+RegEx model when we assume the transcribers are always correct. We see significant improvements for certain entities when using GPT-4 instead of RegExes. It lowers the number of missed matches to almost zero, i.e., GPT-4 always fills in some answer. This increases the number of wrong answers, but also the number of correct answers.

When we add our post-processing component to the evaluation, certificate date and date of death obtain even higher scores. Instead of the GPT scores in Table 3, this results in 96% (+1%) for certificate date and 91% (+3%) for date of death.

Entity	CER (%)	Accuracy (lvst=0)	Accuracy (lvst=3)	Support
Name informant 1	12	36.2%	69.1%	1517
Name informant 2	18	23.1%	59.3%	1505
Name	10	43.4%	87.3%	1527
Name mother	16	45.2%	85.6%	1353
Name father	29	26.0%	77.8%	392
Name partner	22	25.5%	71.2%	184

Table 4: For each name in the 1534 certificates, the Character Error Rate of the HTR+GPT model compared to human transcriptions, and the percentage of fully similar and almost similar answers with a Levenshtein distance ≤ 3 .

Entity	CER (%)	Accuracy (lvst=0)	Accuracy (lvst=3)	Support
Profession informant 1	6	81.4%	92.0%	1517
Profession informant 2	7	73.4%	86.7%	1505
Profession	18	51.5%	76.8%	548
Profession mother	10	71.3%	86.9%	571
Profession father	21	53.2%	70.5%	139
Profession partner	10	65.2%	82.6%	46

Table 5: For each profession in the 1534 certificates, the Character Error Rate of the HTR+GPT model compared to human transcriptions, and the percentage of fully similar and almost similar answers with a Levenshtein distance ≤ 3 . The phrases ‘zonder’, ‘zonder beroep’ and ‘geen’ are excluded.

Table 4 shows the Character Error Rate (CER) of the HTR+GPT output when comparing to the transcriptions of the volunteers, when both are non-empty. These transcriptions are made independently of the HTR output, so the volunteers were not biased by it. Since GPT does not split first and last names, and some names were written last name first, we compare the HTR+GPT output against the combinations 1) ‘first name(s) + ‘last name’ and 2) ‘last name’ + ‘first name(s)’. Then, we take the lowest CER. For the name of the deceased person, we also compare to 3) ‘first name(s)’, because some volunteers used the last name of the parents when the location of the name of the deceased only contained the first name(s)⁵. To better evaluate HTR quality, we take those three combinations into account.

We observe that still about two-third of the HTR names are different than what humans transcribed (= two independent volunteers and a third making the final decision). When we allow for a Levenshtein distance of 3 (three character changes), accuracy improves. Because names are important in the process of linking

⁵When the certificate line mentioning the name of the deceased is: ‘overleden is: Joseph Martes’ and the mother is called ‘Martina Girigorie’, it is unclear whether ‘Martes’ is the last name or a middle name.

persons over various collections, we argue that it is better to keep transcribing names independently of the HTR output to not introduce any biases.

Table 5 shows the HTR+GPT quality of the professions. We exclude all comparisons where either the human transcription or computer output is Null or '#' and exclude the phrases 'zonder', 'zonder beroep' and 'geen'. This to remove the mix-up that negatively influences the scores, and better focus on the HTR quality of the actual professions. As can be seen for professions in Table 3, the accuracy would be much higher if we include the 'correct' empty values.

9 Customisation options

Based on our knowledge on the Curaçao dataset and comparing this with what we learnt about the Suriname dataset, this section describes the strengths and weaknesses of important components in the HANDS-RX pipeline and compares it to other possible components. The HANDS-RX model consists of some interchangeable blocks that have different time efficiency, quality and costs. In general, it can be seen as the more time spent on a component, the better its quality becomes. However, it also increases costs. Also, some components need different levels of proficiency (i.e., does it need a data scientist, historian, or volunteer to execute the task?).

9.1 Layout Analysis components

For the Layout Analysis, one can opt for the simplest solution: Transkribus' default models. Its performance is okay but far from great. Another option is to train custom models, as done in the current implementation of HANDS-RX. We arrived at a great layout detection with only less than 100 input scans due to the homogeneity of the layout.

It is also interchangeable with other software that creates snippets of text. This is because the HTR component needs one-line images. We are not aware of any other existing software, which is solely for creating these snippets. It is often intertwined with the HTR component. Performance in Transkribus is great, so a search for other software is not needed.

9.2 HTR component

To obtain transcriptions, it is not necessary to train one's own models. The Dutchess I. base model can immediately be applied on documents of Dutch language. However, performance can be increased greatly by training custom models. (Table 2). Also, other languages might not have such a high performing base model to begin with.

A downside of using HTR in Transkribus is that transcribing documents costs credits (training is free). In project REE-HDSC, Tjong Kim Sang investigated 'Loghi', free HTR software in current development by The Huygens Institute⁶. Loghi has its own Layout component which cannot be split from the HTR. Tjong Kim Sang tested Loghi's default Layout+HTR and concluded its performance was not great (CER=22%) [5]. This can possibly be improved by training custom models.

There do exist other HTR models, but none with a user interface as Transkribus. So, one needs knowledge of Machine Learning and programming to apply HTR on one's own snippets of text. That is why historians often choose for Transkribus.

9.3 Entity Extraction component

As Entity Extraction component, there exist multiple solutions. Our team tested 1) Regular Expressions, 2) Machine Learning using a Language Model, and 3) GPT models (Large Language Models by OpenAI).

⁶Loghi. <https://github.com/knaw-huc/loghi>

9.3.1 Regular Expressions

Basic Regular Expressions have a low recall but are quickly created by a Data Scientist. With help of documentation and a useful script, historians could also be taught to implement this themselves. However, it might be difficult to obtain high performances, due to the HTR errors in the prior component. We also argue that basic RegExes are undesirable, because it does not balance to the good amount of effort put in earlier components.

More detailed RegExes catch more entities, but need more time, and need to be created by a Data Scientist. An evaluation on the performance can be found in [1]. A repeating downside is that it still suffers a lot from HTR errors. The RegExes try to locate exact word patterns in the transcript, but fail to localise an entity when there is an HTR error in one of the word patterns (surrounding the entity). Research on fuzzy matching allowing 1 to 3 character changes showed this also increased the number of false positives [1].

9.3.2 Machine Learning

Another possibility is training a Machine Learning model. This is free of charge compared to OpenAI's GPT models, but needs a lot of training data to become better than detailed Regular Expressions. So, this would need people to create many ground truth transcriptions ($\pm 1,000$ perhaps less), labelling the entities inside these texts, and a Data Scientist who can train the ML model. Using existing Named Entity Recognition from libraries like Spacy⁷, Flair⁸, NLTK⁹, one can only use default entities, e.g., NAME and LOCATION. To extract entities from death certificates, this always needs own data and training. This has the disadvantage that every project (for a different type of certificate) needs its own customisation, i.e., a ML model trained on death certificates for Curaçao might not be applicable to Surinamese certificates.

9.3.3 GPT models

GPT models are getting more user-friendly as the interface on their online platform minimises the need for programming experience. Their feature called 'batches' uses a JSONL file containing an API call on each line. This can easily be made with a Python script.¹⁰ Also, the prompt engineering part can be learned by historians, as the prompt can be similar to a guideline written for volunteers. OpenAI's interface makes it easy to test different prompts, but a Python script is needed again to transform OpenAI's output to a table with entities. We gave the historians a crash course on this process. Historians with a bit of knowledge on programming should be able to execute our Python script, however, it might be difficult to solve bugs if the script does not work on the fly.

10 Paramaribo dataset

HDSC wishes to execute the HANDS-RX pipeline on another dataset from Suriname. These are death certificates from Paramaribo between 1929 and 1960. It consists of 15,243 scans of which years 1929-1945 have one certificate per page (i.e., two per scan) and years 1946-1960 have two certificates per page (i.e., four per scan). We decided to split these certificates into separate images, because it makes processing in Transkribus easier (for both the machine's layout detection and the volunteers creating the training data). We will teach Transkribus to ignore parts of the certificates on the sides.

We wrote a function that cuts the image in 2 or 4 parts, taking a large margin of 200 pixels at each cut. This minimises the risk of losing information, e.g., when pages are slightly diagonal. This threshold is determined by looking at a couple of example cuts, and can be different for other type of data.

⁷Spacy. <https://spacy.io/>

⁸Flair. <https://github.com/flairNLP/flair>

⁹NLTK. <https://www.nltk.org/>

¹⁰This Python script is included on our GitHub page.

We end up with about 40,000 certificates that will be processed using a customised HTR+GPT model built in a successive project. We end this project preparing 10x50 random datasets that volunteers will correct to use as training data. We used the same layout models as used in [1] (P2PaLA_Curacao_bestModel, LA_Curacao), and our best HTR model (Curacao_Dutchess), because they worked surprisingly well on our new data. After this data is corrected on both layout and HTR by the volunteers, we will have ground truth sets to train our custom P2PaLA, baseline and HTR models. These will then be used to process all certificates. Meanwhile, a prompt for GPT-4 will be created. This successive project can re-use all software with some tweaks needed like a custom GPT-4 prompt. Our end product is again a table with all entity values.

11 Image clustering

This section describes our image clustering method performed on the 15,243 Surinamese death certificate scans from Paramaribo 1929-1960. HDSC calls for an automatic filtering method, because the set is too large to do this manually. Two other reasons are 1) to find interesting scans (e.g., those that are not death certificates), and 2) to reduce noise when these scans are processed. This clustering method can easily be tuned to work on other image datasets as well.

Our filtering method consists of two steps. First, filtering out the vertical (portrait) images. Second, applying an image clustering algorithm. Most scans are landscape-oriented. We decided to apply the image clustering on both the original scans and the split pages, so we would find abnormalities in both. This report, however, only evaluates the clustering on the original images. The clustering on the split pages is moved to the successive project.

We use the DBscan clustering algorithm¹¹, because it is suited for uneven distributions. We expect one big main cluster containing ‘normal’ certificates, and various tiny clusters with specific features. We expect that the split of 2 or 4 certificates is not visible in the clustering, because these scans look too similar. An example of scans that can be filtered are blank pages, i.e., half of the scan is white. DBscan clustering also creates one group of noise; these scans fall outside the previously specified clusters.

After applying DBscan clustering, we obtain one main group (size=13,369), 16 small groups (size 3-24) and one group filled with the remaining noise (size=1,546). We manually inspected the 16 groups and find each group consists of visually-similar scans. However, they do not contain interesting exceptions, so we treat them as ‘normal’ certificates.

We suspect the exceptions from ‘normal’ scans are in the noise-group. We manually inspected all 1,546 scans and moved them into another folder if they deviated from a ‘normal’ scan. These folders we called ‘some_empty’ (if some certificates on the scan are not filled in), ‘vertical_marginalia’, (if we see marginalia with vertically written text), ‘no_info’ (e.g., title page or ending page) and ‘misc’ (other miscellaneous scans, e.g., blurry scans). In total, we only moved 175 of the 1,546 scans to one of these four folders. All others looked like ‘normal’ certificates in our opinion. See Figure 4 for examples of each category.

A potential risk is that our clustering method performs poorly and we encountered the abnormal scans by coincidence. To invalidate this thought, we inspected 500 random scans from the main cluster. Every single one of them was a normal certificate. In our noise-group, 11% was not a normal certificate. Thus, we conclude our image-clustering method is effective in downsizing the dataset from 15,243 to 1,546 scans that needs manual inspection on noise (90% decrease).

Unfortunately, the algorithm could not pick up on text-related features, such as stillborn certificates, migrant certificates, or verdicts. Also, the layout of 2-certificate and 4-certificate format is too similar. The image clustering did find empty pages, invalid certificates (recognised by a big cross over the certificate), blurry scans, vertical marginalia, and more. We learnt that the Paramaribo 1929-1960 dataset was already

¹¹DBscan clustering. <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.cluster.DBSCAN.html>

(a) A 'normal' scan with four certificates.

(b) A vertical scan.

(c) A scan with one empty page.

(d) A scan with vertical text.

(e) A scan that does not have any information, besides ending the register.

(f) A scan in the miscellaneous category containing one invalid certificate.

Figure 4. 6 Examples of scans from the Paramaribo 1929-1960 death certificates.

quite clean to begin with. A quick run on death certificates from Curaçao showed us that it is also suitable to find ripped pieces. So, this image clustering method can help speed up the process of analysing and filtering a dataset based on clear visual differences.

12 Concluding remarks

This project processed ~24,000 death certificates from Curaçao between 1879-1895, 1905-1909, 1930-1939, and 1945-1949. We started with a HTR+RegEx pipeline, but experiments with GPT-4 showed more correct matches were found for all entities. Changing to the HTR+GPT pipeline also led to more false answers, but we argue that the number of empty entries for HTR+RegEx was too high and undesirable for volunteers in a review project. Overall, performance increased, as GPT is more flexible for HTR errors than static RegExes that failed. We believe the HTR+GPT output is suited to be checked by volunteers in a review project, along with names and professions transcribed the traditional way.

A limitation is that evaluation is only done on years 1879-1881. Especially, years after 1938 are slightly different in layout and printed text. Our P2PaLA region correction technique did not work well on these sets, so it could be that some regions do not align the certificate perfectly. We are also not aware of the GPT-4 performance on other years outside 1879-1881.

For future work, we suggest taking a random sample including all processed years and manually review them to get a better performance estimate. Or, wait for the citizen science projects that will check these outputs and compare. Additionally, we explained the possibility of adding a profession-component that rewrites professions based on a gazetteer (Section 3.6). It also remains an open question how exactly names should be split into first, middle and last names. [1] already showed the possible conventions officials could have used when writing the certificate. During this project, we also learnt that volunteers have difficulty determining the split. If it is already unclear for us humans, it is understandable that GPT-4 did not succeed in making this split effectively either. Using the HTR+GPT output and multiple gazetteers with names and professions, some data analysis would be useful to find patterns in how names should be split.

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